

MADHUMEHA (DIABETES MELLITUS) IN AYURVEDIC LITERATURE: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Diabetes Mellitus is one of the leading non-communicable disease contribute to death and disability. Its complications pose a major threat to public health resources throughout the world. In India it has become a major health care problem with an estimated 66.8 million people suffering from the condition, representing the largest number of any country in the world. Etiological factors described in Ayurveda literature, signs and symptoms, complications of *Madhumeha* closely relate to Diabetes Mellitus. *Madhumeha* has been extensively described in ayurvedic texts under the broad umbrella of *Prameha*. *Madhumeha* is type of *vataj prameha*. Causative factors like dietary factors, life style factors & psychological factors, prodromal symptoms, signs and symptoms, complications of *Madhumeha* are very well explained. Etiological factors of *Madhumeha* are similar to causes of diabetes. Researches have

proven the efficacy of drugs and therapies mentioned in Ayurvedic texts for *Madhumeha* as potent as in management of Type 2 Diabetes mellitus. Stress, sleep deprivations, obstructive sleep apnoea have emerged as newer causes of Type 2 Diabetes mellitus. Prodromal symptoms like *alasya* and others, signs & symptoms *prabhoota* and *avila mootrata*, complications like *pootimamsa* etc of *Madhumeha* appears at different stages of diabetes. In this article review of *Madhumeha* from classic ayurvedic texts is put together, *kriya- kala* of *Prameha* is drawn. *Nidana*, *poorvaroopa*, *roopa* and *upadrava* of *Madhumeha* are discussed in diabetes according to modern sciences.

KEYWORDS: *Prameha*, *Madhumeha*, Type 2 Diabetes mellitus, Non- communicable disease, Life style disorder.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes Mellitus is a non- communicable disease. According to WHO in 2014, 8.5% of adults aged 18 years and older had diabetes. In 2015, diabetes was direct cause of 1.6 million deaths.^[1] In India it has become a major health care problem with an estimated 66.8 million people suffering from the condition, representing the largest number of any country in the world.^[2] The word diabetes mellitus has been derived from two words, *diabetes* (Greek) which means 'siphon through' and *mellitus* (Latin) which means 'sweetened with honey'.^[3] Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic disorder characterized by high blood sugar level for prolonged period with disturbances of carbohydrate, fat and protein metabolism resulting from deficit in insulin secretion, action or both. There are three basis types of Diabetes Mellitus: Type 1 Diabetes mellitus, Type 2 Diabetes mellitus and Gestational diabetes.^[4,5] Symptoms of Diabetes mellitus can be enumerated as 3Ps i.e polyuria-need to urinate frequently, polydipsia- increased thirst and fluid intake, polyphagia- increased appetite.^[6] Etiology of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, its complications, poor prognosis and alarming rise in its incidences all over the world has drawn attention of concerned scientists, physicians and others. Its etiology, symptoms, complications and prognosis correlate with *Madhumeha*. There have been constant researches by ayurveda scholars, preachers and practisers on *Prameha* and *Madhumeha*. Researches proved efficacy of drugs, pathya-apthaya studies described in ayurvedic texts in management of Type 2 Diabetes mellitus. '*Madhumeha Mission*.^[7]' was being observed in India by government of India from 28th Oct 2016 to draw attention towards morbidity and mortality caused by this disease and to have a definite standard treatment regime.

Literary resources: *Madhumeha* is described under broad umbrella of *Prameha*. The word 'Prameha' consists of two sub-words. When root 'Mih' is added with prefix 'Pra' the word becomes 'Prameha'. This means *Prameha* is a disease in which a person urinates frequently and profusely. *Madhumeha* is a type of vataj *Prameha*. *Madhumeha* also consist of two words *madhu* and *mih*. It means excessive honey like sweet urination.^[8] Mention of *Madhumeha* is not only confined to *Brihtrayi*. It goes back into vedic times but in rudimentary form. According to Hindu mythology Lord Ganesha is the first to suffer from *Madhumeha* due to excessive, uncontrolled eating habits and heavy body constitution.^[9]

In vedic literature the evolution of *Madhumeha* can be traced in Atharvaveda. In Atharvaveda there is a reference related to the disease 'Asrava' along with its management. Sayanacharya has opined that *Asrava* means '*Mutraatisara*'. The English translator Whitney (1962) interpreted it as morbid flow of urine, While Leman has translated the meaning of *Asarva* as Diabetes Mellitus.^[10] Details about *Madhumeha* begin from Samhita period. Prognosis of *Madhumeha* seemed difficult for veterans and so is today therefore scholars called *Madhumeha* as one among *Asta-Mahagada*.^[11] Another one-word explanation is *Prameha anusanginaam* i.e *Prameha* is a chronic disorder which do not get resolved completely.^[12] According to Acharya Vagabatta in his book *Astanga hrdayama* condition in which the urine resemble honey and becomes sweet is called *Madhumeha*.^[13] In the most popular ancient literature of Ayurvedic science, Acharya Charaka has described three main types of *Prameha* on the basis of Dosha and twenty subtypes of *Prameha*. A separate chapter has been described on *Prameha* in Nidanasthan 4th and Chikitsasthan 6th. The etiology, pathogenesis, symptomatology, complications and treatment of *Madhumeha* have been explained under the broad heading of *Prameha*. In Sushruta Samhita Acharya Sushruta also explained the *Prameha* in elaborative manner with separate chapter on its management. He used term '*Kshaudrameha*'.^[14] synonym for *Madhumeha* in Nidana 6th chapter. The most notable contribution of Acharya Sushruta was to give a separate chapter on the treatment of *Madhumeha* in Chikitsasthana 13 and first time he described its specific treatment. Vagbhatacharya classified the urinary disorders under the broad headings of '*Mutraatipravrttija vyadhi*' and '*Mutrpravrttija vyadhi*'. He categorized *Prameha* including *Madhumeha* as '*Mutraatipravrttija vyadhi*'.^[15] He has described two types of *Madhumeha* i.e. *Dhatukshyat* and *Avaranatvat*.^[16] In Harita samhita, *Madhumeha* has been mentioned as *Papajanya vyadhi*. Here 13 types of *Prameha* with nomenclature different than above treatise like, *Puyameha*, *Ghritameha* are enumerated.

Acharya Madhavakara in his book *Madhavnidana* has collectively repeated the description of Charakasamhita, Sushrutasamhita and *Astanga Hridaya* in chapter *Pramehanidanam*. Gayadas explained the *avilamutrata* because of the presence of *Dooshya* in it. Acharya Sarangadhara in *Sarangadhara Samhita* has mentioned the 20 subtypes of *Prameha* with *Madhumeha* in *Prathama Khanda* 7th chapter and gave brief description. Bhavaprakash has explained *Prameha* and *Madhumeha* disease along with herbal remedies, he added some new herbo-mineral preparations for its management.^[17] Research continued on *Madhumeha*, it can be traced from commentaries of Chakrapani, Dalhana and others. In present era many researches

went hand in hand for *Madhumeha* and Diabetes. Results proved that *Madhumeha* is closely related to Type 2 Diabetes mellitus. Causes, pathogenesis, premonitory symptoms, symptoms, and complications of *Madhumeha* are quite similar to Type 2 Diabetes mellitus. More advancement in research techniques helped finding newer causative factors, symptoms and complications which are prevalent today.

Nidana (etiological factors): Causes of *Prameha* are explained in Charak Prameha Nidanasthana. These etiological factors can be categorised as *aaharaja* (dietary habits), *viharaja* (physical work-out or daily activities) and *mansika* (mental status) of an individual. To sum up Acharya Charak concluded *nidanas* which causes excessive accumulation of *kapha*, *meda* and *mutra* in body are causes of *Prameha*.^[18] Causative factors for *Madhumeha* are same as *Prameha* along with factors responsible for vitiation of *vata* in body. Similar causative factors are explained in 6th chapter in chikitsasthana i.e Prameha chikitsa. Similar factors are explained by Acharya Sushruta and Acharya Vagabhatta. In Madhav nidana same shloka has been quoted by Acharya Madhav regarding causative factors as Charaka chikitsasthana.^[19] According to below mentioned causes this type of *Madhumeha* is *Apathyanimittaja* as explained by Acharya Sushruta.^[20] These factors are in accordance with etiological factors responsible for Type 2 Diabetes mellitus. Genetic factors/ hereditary causes have also been described as *sahaj prameha*.^[21]

Nidana	Ch	Su	Va	Ma
Aahara: Haayanak (new rice), yavak (barley), cheenak (millet), uddalak, utkat, Mukund, mahavrihi, pramodaka, suganhdaka (varieties of rice).	+			
Navanna (freshly harvested grains), ghee, nava harenu, (new pulses, peas, black gram).	+		+	
Aanup gramya jaliya mamasa (flesh of domestic, wetland & aquatic animals).	+		+	
Saka (excessive green leafy vegetable).	+			
Til (sesame seeds), palala, pista anna (carbohydrate rich food).	+		+	
Paayas (milk), vilepi (thick rice soup), krishra (milk pudding).	+		+	+
Ikshuvikara (preparations of jaggery).	+		+	
Nava maddh (new crude alcohol)/				

Sura (alcohol).	+		+	+
Mandak (unformed curd), dadhi (curd).			+	
madhura drava(Excessive sweet items).	+		+	
Excessive intake of Sheeta(cold), snigdha(unctuous), meda (fatty), dravya anna and pana.	+	+		
Vihara: Mrijavarjana (avoidance of body cleanliness)				
vyaayama varjana (avoidance of exercise),	+			
swapana sayan aasana prasanga (pleasure of sedentary habits and sleep).	+	+		+
Indulgence in Divaswapa (day sleep)				
Mansika: Aalsya(laziness).				
Eksthana aasana rati, sayan (pleasure in sitting or lying), vidhi varjita (improper or no practice of panchkarma).		+		
		+	+	

For development of *Prameha / Madhumeha*, repeated acceptance of above factors causes vitiation of *tridosha* and 10 *dushyas* especially *meda*, *mamsa* and *kleda*. According to Charaka *Prameha* is a *tridoshaja* morbidity, but among *dosha bahu drava sleshma* and *bahu abdha meda* are must for development of any type of *Prameha*.^[22] In Brihtri there is mention of 10 *dushyas* which get vitiated. These *dushyas* are *meda*, *mamsa*, *sareera kleda*, *sukra*, *sonita*, *vasa*, *majja*, *lasika*, *rasa*, *oja*.^[23] *Dosha Kapha* and *dushya Meda* are vitiated in all types of *prameha*.^[24]

Dushya	Ch	Su	Va	Ma
Bahu abadda Meda(excessive loose fat)	+		+	+
Mamsa (muscles)	+	+	+	+
Sareera kleda (moisture of body)	+		+	+
Sukra (semen)	+		+	+
Sonita (blood)	+	+	+	+
Vasa (muscle fat)	+	+	+	+
Majja (bone marrow)	+	+	+	+
Lasika (lymph)	+	+	+	+
Rasa (plasma)	+		+	+
Oja Sweda (sweat)	+		+	+

Purvaroopo (prodromal symptoms): Poorvaroopo of *Prameha* are explained more elaborately by Charaka in nidanasthana as well as in chikitsasthana.^[25,26] By Sushruta & Vagabhatta in nidana sthana.^[27,28] Madhav also opined the similar poorvaroopo. No special appearance of poorva roopa before development of Madhumeha, it is so because according to Sushruta *Madhumeha* occurs when any type of *Prameha* be it *kaphaja*, *pittaja* or *vataja* is neglected or poorly treated. It is incurable stage of *Prameha*.^[29]

Poorvaroopo	Ch	Su	Va	Ma
Jatilibhava kesha (matting of hairs)	+	+		
Madhuraasya (sweet taste in mouth).	+	+	+	+
Karpadyo suptata/daha (numbness & burning sensation in hands & feet).	+	+	+	+
Mukh talu kantha sosha (dryness of mouth, palate & throat).	+		+	
Pipasa/ sheet priyta (thirst)				
Aalasya (laziness)	+	+	+	+
Sada (malaise)	+			
Mala kaya (increased excrements in body)	+	+		
Kayachidra updeha (increased discharge in orifices of body)	+			
Paridaha suptata anga (thermalgia & numbness in body)	+			
Sareera- mutra satpad- pipilika abhisaran (attraction of insects & ants to body & urine)			+	
Mutra dosha (abnormalities in urine).	+			
Madhura-sukla mutra (sweet, turbid urine).			+	
Vishr sareera gandha (bad body odor),	+	+		
Sweda- angagandha.				
Nidra tandra, sada(malaise) sarvakaalam (sleep & continuous torpor).	+	+	+	
Sithilangata (flabbiness of body)			+	
Sayiya, asana swapnasukhe rati (pleasure to remain in bed for prolonged sleep).	+		+	
Hridya netra jihwa, danta updeha (accumulation of dirt in palate, throat, tongue and teeth).	+		+	
Kesha-nakha ativridhi (excessive			+	

growth of nails and hairs).				
Snigdha- pichhila- guru gatra(stikyness, slimy and heaviness in body).	+	+	+	+
Deha Chikannata (slippery and unctuous body).	+	+	+	+
		+		

Roopa (signs & symptoms): ‘*Samanya laxana prabhuta avil mutrata*’ i.e excessive turbid urine passage is common symptom of all types of Prameha.^[30,31] Madhav added along with excessive urine, vitiated *dosha* and *dhusya* properties also appear in urine and make it turbid. Thus nomenclature of type of *Prameha* is decided. In *Madhumeha* excessive *kshaya*, *madhura*, *pandu*, and *ruksha* urine is passed.^[32]

Roopa	Ch	Su	Va	Ma
Prabhoota avila mutrata (excessive turbid urination), Kshaya(astringent) & Madhura(sweet), pandu (yellowish- white)ruksha meha.	+	+	+	+
ksaudra rasa varna meha(urine resembling honey in taste and colour),	+			+
Madhusama meha (urine resembling honey in taste & appearance),	+	+	+	+
Kshodra rasa, varna meha				

Stages of manifestation of *Madhumeha* as per *Kriyakala*: Understanding of *Kriyakala* helps in early diagnosis and treatment of any disease. *Kriyakala* are stages of development of a disease.

Sanchaya

Nidan sewan: Complete aversion of physical exertion, excessive sleep during day and night, excessive intake of meat of animals residing near watery or marshy areas, excessive intake of milk and milk products, intake of newly harvested grains, consumption of new and crude liquor. Excessive intake of sweet or food items made up of sugar or jaggery. Desire of sleep or rest whole day and lead stress-free life. *Shleshma Meda Mootra* causing diet and activities.

According to ayurvedic texts *Madhumeha* manifests in people leading a sedentary and stress-free life. But unlike *Madhumeha* Type 2 Diabetes mellitus is equally seen in rich and poor. It is more prevalent in middle to low income countries. In modern era no or little physical work, sedentary life at home and work place, changed dietary patterns like junk food and western diet pattern are similar to *apthayanimitajja nidana* of *Madhumeha*. Stress, deficit sleep has emerged as newer causes of Type 2 Diabetes mellitus. Obstructive sleep apnoea (OSA) is pervasive among overweight and obese adults, it has become a novel, modifiable risk factor relevant to insulin resistance, glucose intolerance and development of Type 2 Diabetes mellitus.^[33] Cause of *Madhumeha* like *aasyasaukhama* can be directly applied to Type 2 Diabetes mellitus because diet patterns prevalent today like junk foods, processed food items, sugar sweetened beverages, western pattern diet are full of excess of calories. Now-days people purchase cereals from market which are usually of new harvest with pesticides added to them. Common among the two clinical entities is that both diet patterns cause obesity, dyslipidemia (*meda dhatu* vitiation). Advancement in diagnostic tools for Type 2 Diabetes mellitus have proved that there is not only presence of hyperglycaemia but also associated abnormal lipid profile i.e dyslipidemia.^[34,35] Ayurvedic scholars laid stress on vitiation of *Medha dhatu*. Among all the treatises of Ayurveda there is mention of *poorva roopa* of *Prameha / Madhumeha*. But in today's scenario when there are ranges for deciding pre-diabetic and diabetic condition few *poorvaroopta* exists as signs, symptoms and complications instead of prodromal symptoms in pre-diabetic stage. Like *pipasa* (thirst) or *mukh-talukantha sosha* is considered as an important sign of Diabetes as Polydipsia. *Supta anga/daha* appears during diabetic neuropathies. *Visra sareera gandha, madhura-asya, pipilika sareera abhisarana* can be co related with stage of Diabetic Ketoacidosis, when body have a fruity smell due to acetone bodies. *Roopa* of both *Prameha* or *Madhumeha* are summed up in one sentence as passage of abnormal quality and quantity of urine along with *dushya* whereas the commonest signs of Type 2 Diabetes mellitus are polydipsia, polyphagia and polyuria. *Upadrava* (complications) like *atisara* (diarrhoea), *trisana*(thirst) occur during Diabetic ketoacidosis along with other symptoms. *Putimamsa, pidika, alaji, vidradhi* can be compared with ulcers, carbuncles or pustules or other skin infections which manifest due to prolonged hyperglycemia and compromised immune system of body in Type 2 Diabetes mellitus.^[36] Dietary changes and life style modifications as per *Madhumeha* have shown significant decline in hyperglycemia and improvement in symptoms of type 2 Diabetes mellitus.

CONCLUSION

The disease *Madhumeha* is well documented in ancient literature. Researches proved *Avaranjanya apattyanimitajja Madhumeha* have similarities with Type 2 Diabetes mellitus.

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